

SYNTHESIS OF SUBSTITUTED DINITROPHENYL KETONES AND PHENYLACETIC ACIDS. PART II

BY A. B. SEN AND P. M. BHARGAVA

2 : 6-Dinitro-4-bromophenyl-acetone and -acetic acid have been prepared.

In the previous part of this series (*this Journal*, 1947, 24, 268) it has been shown that substituted phenylketones and phenylacetic acids can be obtained in good yields by submitting the condensation products of acetoacetic ester and polynitro aromatic compounds containing reactive halogen atom to ketonic and acid hydrolysis respectively.

In the present paper this reaction has been extended to the preparation of 2 : 6-dinitro-4-bromophenylacetone and 2 : 6-dinitro-4-bromophenylacetic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

2 : 6-Dinitro-4-bromophenylacetoacetic Ester.—Ethyl acetoacetate (5.2 c.c.) was added, with stirring, to 0.92 g. of sodium and 20 c.c. of ether contained in a bolt-head flask fitted with a condenser and a mechanical stirrer. This was heated on the water-bath until the last traces of sodium had disappeared. To the cooled solution was added 1-chloro-4-bromo-2 : 6-dinitrobenzene (5.6 g.), the mixture refluxed for 6 hours with constant stirring and then allowed to stand for 12 hours. The ethereal solution was first extracted with water and then with 1% sodium hydroxide; the combined extracts were then acidified with dilute nitric acid, when a red oil separated out. The aqueous layer was decanted, the residual oil dissolved in an excess of cold alcohol and then left for crystallisation. Two crops of crystals were obtained on partial evaporation of the alcohol. The first crop consisted of yellow and the second, of dark red crystals. These two crops of crystals were combined and further purified by the same method when yellow needles were obtained, m. p. 97°, yield 98% of theory. (Found : N, 7.47. $C_{12}H_{11}O_7N_2Br$ requires N, 7.25 per cent).

2 : 6-Dinitro-4-bromophenylacetone.—Finely powdered 2 : 6-dinitro-4-bromophenylacetoacetic ester (1.5 g.) was dissolved in 15 c.c. of concentrated sulphuric acid and 7 c.c. of water were then added to it under constant stirring. A brisk evolution of CO_2 commenced; when the evolution of CO_2 had ceased, the solution was poured on ice. The ketone which separated out was filtered and recrystallised from hot alcohol as colourless needles, m. p. 133-34°, yield quantitative. (Found : N, 9.47. $C_9H_7O_5N_2Br$ requires N, 9.24 per cent).

The phenylhydrazone was prepared by dissolving the above ketone (0.5 g.) in about 10 c.c. of alcohol and adding to it about 8 drops of phenylhydrazine and refluxing the mixture for 15 minutes. The phenylhydrazone separated out from this solution on cooling. Recrystallised from hot alcohol as fine yellow needles it melts at 126-27°, yield theoretical. (Found : N, 14.17. $C_{15}H_{13}O_4N_4Br$ requires N, 14.25 per cent).

The oxime was prepared by adding 0.5 g. of hydroxylamine sulphate to a solution of the above ketone (1 g.) in alcohol, and a drop of phenolphthalein, followed by a solution of caustic soda dropwise until a permanent red colour was obtained. This mixture was refluxed for about an hour, cooled, and then poured in 30 c.c. of water, and left in a refrigerator overnight. The precipitate which separated out was filtered and washed with cold alcohol, when a yellow crystalline product was left behind, m. p. 93-94°, yield 75% of theory. (Found : N, 12.78. $C_9H_4O_5N_3Br$ requires N, 13.20 per cent).

2 : 6-Dinitro-4-bromophenylacetic Acid.—2 : 4-Dinitro-4-bromophenylacetoacetic ester (1 g.) was refluxed for half an hour with 5 c.c. of 20% alcoholic potash. The alcohol was then distilled off and the residue acidified with dilute HCl, when a solid product separated out. This was dissolved in hot alcohol, filtered, and the filtrate allowed to evaporate. The first crop consisted of yellowish needles of the unchanged ester and was rejected. The second crop, obtained as brown scales of m. p. 184°, proved to be the desired acid, yield 80% of theory. (Found : N, 8.87. $C_8H_5O_6N_2Br$ requires N, 9.18 per cent).

2 : 6-Dinitro-4-bromophenylmalonic Ester.—To the sodium derivative of ethyl malonate, prepared from sodium (0.92 g.) and malonic ester (6.4 g.) in 25 c.c. of ether, was added 5.6 g. of 1-chloro-2 : 6-dinitro-4-bromobenzene, suspended in ether. The mixture was refluxed for 6 hours and allowed to stand overnight. The ethereal mixture was extracted first with water and then with 1% NaOH and the combined extracts acidified with dilute nitric acid, when a red oil separated. The aqueous portion was decanted, the oil dissolved in alcohol and left to crystallise by itself. Recrystallisation was effected by redissolving it in alcohol, filtering and allowing the filtrate to evaporate, when brownish red needles were obtained, m. p. 101°, yield 90% of theory. (Found : N, 6.88. $C_{13}H_{12}O_8N_2Br$ requires N, 6.91 per cent).

2 : 6-Dinitro-4-bromophenylacetic Acid.—The above ester (2 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (6 c.c.), and a mixture of 15 c.c. of water and 1 c.c. of conc. sulphuric acid was added to it. It was hydrolysed on a free but low flame for two hours under a reflux condenser when the colour of the mixture changed to dark brown and then to red. On cooling in ice, the acid separated out which was then allowed to settle. The supernatant liquid was decanted off, the residue in the flask dissolved in alcohol and the solvent allowed to evaporate when the acid crystallised out, yield 90% of theory, m. p. 184° (identical with the m. p. of the acid obtained by hydrolysis of 2 : 6-dinitro 4-bromophenylacetoacetic ester) (Found : N, 8.51. $C_8H_5O_6N_2Br$ requires N, 9.18 per cent).